

USEFUL CREATIVE TECHNIQUES PROPOSED FOR TEACHING CHILDREN

Gadayeva Gulshan Farkhod kyzy,

The student of the faculty foreign languages

TashkentSPU named after Nizami, Uzbekistan

Scientific advisor: E.T.Tursunnazarova

Annotation: Currently, one of the main problems of modern school is the fall of students' interest in learning. The question arises, what form of training to use, so that the motivational potential is aimed at a more effective development of the educational program by schoolchildren. First of all, teachers need to take into account age-related psychophysical features, use various forms of work, taking into account the fact that students' interest in assignments disappears in 10-15 minutes, therefore, the methods of teaching in secondary schools should be accompanied with frequent changes of activities in the classroom.

Keywords: collage technique, dramatization, games, creative grammar, creative atmosphere, activities.

Аннотация: На сегодняшний день одной из главных проблем современной школы является падение интереса учащихся к учебе. Встает вопрос, какую форму для обучения использовать, чтобы мотивационный потенциал был направлен на более эффективное освоение школьниками образовательной программы. Прежде всего учителям необходимо учитывать возрастные психофизические особенности, использовать разнообразные формы работы, учитывая тот факт, что интерес к заданиям у учащихся исчезает через 10-15 минут, поэтому методика преподавания в общеобразовательной школе предусматривает частую смену видов деятельности на уроке.

Ключевые понятие: техника коллажа, драматизация, игры, креативная грамматика, креативная атмосфера, упражнения.

All materials should be focused on different types of perception: sound, practical action, writing and visual support. One of the great methods of work is the technology of using a collage on lessons in elementary school. The use of collage technology as a means of learning dramatically expands teachers' capabilities in choosing materials and forms of learning activities, makes the lessons bright and exciting, informative and emotionally rich.

The undoubted advantage of this kind of work is the condition that every student, even the weakest and least psychologically active, has the opportunity to show his own imagination and creativity, activity and independence. This technique allows students to familiarize themselves with any thematic material and serves as the most effective form of education. In addition, this type of work has a great educational value, because it aims to develop social competence among younger students, that is, the ability to act independently, choosing their work strategy to develop a sense of responsibility for the final result, the ability to speak publicly and reasonably present the final result.

The collage technique is designed in such a way that the work can be done not only individually, but also in pairs or in groups. The productivity of students and the goal they pursue is in teachers' hands.

The advantage of creating collages in traditional form and using paper and stationery is that at the end of the work, the teacher can decorate the class with collages of students which can serve as an excellent hint and reminder of the rules they studied during lessons instead of boring textbook tables.

In addition, the method of work as a creative grammar is mostly used during Russian and English lessons, since language learning is impossible in isolation. Children become aware of grammatical phenomena and apply them in their written work as long as they begin to read texts from the perspective of the author.

Later, learners explain the rules of punctuation on the basis of their own texts, the contents of which they set out and experience. The study and creative refraction of these texts are one of the primary productive grammar trainings.

Children at any age love to write, invent, fantasize, so writing tales for many students is a favorite activity. Writing fairy tales, essays and letters in foreign languages develops lexical and grammatical knowledge, skills and abilities of all types of speech activities. Moreover, reading fairy tales is useful at any age as they bring up friendliness, love of native and other countries' culture. Pupils, performing tasks in writing independently look up the correct spelling of words in a dictionary; they memorize spelling, translation and the semantic meaning of words more easily. Such activity contributes to the development of children's thinking, memory and attention. Using cartoons in class and further performing game tasks for them both arouses learners' interests and enhances knowledge; playing songs in English or reading fairy tales during classes can lead to broadening creativity and mentality. Therefore, it is impossible to neglect such creative methods as an inspiring learning environment and dramatization. Such a creative atmosphere inspires not only children, but also teachers. The bright expositions of children's works and small oases of creativity delight eyes. In a comfortable environment, students can take advantage of the proposed literature and a variety of visual aids. Learning poems with students and playing them in roles in the class allows the teacher to solve two problems at once: to additionally work on the pronunciation of students and create an atmosphere of ease and relaxation in class.

Grammar games are of great interest for children that allow them to develop their creative activity, create a natural situation for the use of new speech patterns containing certain grammatical difficulties. This type of games includes important grammatical material, namely the verbs: be, have, may, can, must, construction is there, tense verb forms of the group Indefinite, Continuous, Perfect, subjunctive, indirect speech. Children especially like phonetic exercise games. With the help of such games, children learn to read poems loudly and clearly, they practice pronouncing English sounds. The role of the teacher is especially important in these games: his own freedom of movement, imagination, enthusiasm must affect students, attract them with his own charisma.

Dramatization: Dramatization is the most powerful pedagogical tool that promotes rest, causing positive emotions, lightness and pleasure. This technique allows you to develop students' imaginations, reveal their talents and inspire them with new ideas for further oral and written assignments. Teachers use a variety of dramatization techniques, contributing to the study of characters and their characters, historical events and problematic situations. It is primarily known fact that a child is a great imitator. Imitating, the child is not just ape – it is an act of real creativity. This process also has a positive effect on the emotional state of the child.

The use of various games helps to inspire children with a foreign language, creates conditions for success in learning a language [3, 6]. Children learn playfully, improving their knowledge of a foreign language. In English, you can play the game “Dress up a doll” on the theme “Clothes”, the purpose of which is to teach you to understand the statements and use them in your own monologue statements. So, students make dolls and clothes for her at home and dress their dolls in different outfits by the teacher's command, for example: put on the coat, take off the coat, put on the dress, take off the dress, put on... and so on. And do the same in a pair, keeping the teacher's intonation. Or you can captivate students and play a puppet show / puppet show, the goal of the lesson is to develop monologue and dialogical speech. Children, putting a finger doll on their hands, lose dialogue in pairs or in mini groups, as well as building a monologue on various topics in the situation of everyday communication on the topics of “acquaintance”, “in the store” and so on. In the pedagogical process various games are widely used as a means of methodology and technology of training. Each game is unique, hence contains various functions that contributes to the development of students' cognitive activity. Each type of games helps in the development of the child, both a healthy person and a healthy personality. So, with the proper selection of methods and techniques, teachers can plan and create effective conditions for the normal development and socialization of the child.

References:

1. Бебянко Е. А. Драматизация в обучении английскому языку / Е. А. Бебянко. – Ростов н/Д: Феникс, 2013. – 93 с.
2. Ибука М. После трех уже поздно. – М.: «Альпина нон-фикшн», 2014. – 223с.
3. Красюк В. В., Красюк Н. И. Стихи и игры на английском языке / сост. Красюк В. В., Красюк Н. И. – 3-е изд. – Ростов н/Д: Феникс, 2015. – 96 с